

Drivers of Cashless Payments in Emerging Markets

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Abstract : *Cashless payments are gaining popularity around the world. Countries are competing to build digital payment ecosystems in order to accelerate the adoption of cashless payments. The purpose of this study is to find out what drives cashless payments in emerging markets. The panel data regression method was used to analyse a panel data collection of nine emerging market economies. The research demonstrates the significant impact of internet use on cashless payments. The amount of cards has a detrimental impact on the outcome. Internet based payments are becoming more popular which is easy and convenient method of cashless payments.*

Keywords : Cashless Payments, Electronic Payments, Digital Payments, Emerging Markets, Panel Data.

1. Introduction

The global growth of cashless payments shows an upward trend. Adoption of innovative technologies in the financial service sector accelerates the growth of cashless payment systems. Countries are largely promoting cashless payments by facilitating simplified and easily accessible digital payment ecosystems. Mobile payments, card payments, and NFC payments technologies provide convenience and help to reach every segment of the population. The outbreak of covid-19 also accelerates the growth of cashless and contactless payments. People depend on technology to find safe and efficient payment transactions, which enables social distancing. (Daqar et al., 2021; Anderson et al., 2020). Low- and lower-middle-income countries stepped up to fulfil the growing demand for digital payment needs during the outbreak (Mansour, 2021).

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The global fintech lenders paved a new way to provide financial services and it is going to shape the future of banking (Murinde et al., 2022). It helps to bring banking services to remote locations, thus providing financial inclusion. Global markets are moving towards a digital economy, and finTech promotes digital economy growth by encouraging technology innovations (Xiaohui et al., 2022). Apart from developed economies, emerging markets have great potential for cashless payment growth. They are adopting the latest fintech ecosystems and facilitating cashless payment growth by utilising the growth of GDP and large human resources.

The purpose of the present study is to identify the drivers of cashless payments in the emerging markets. In order to find this objective, the study used a panel data set of nine emerging economies. Selected macroeconomic variables were analysed using panel data regression method and fixed and random effect models. The rest of the paper is organised as follows. Section II summarised the literature related to the study. Data and methodology were discussed in section III. The result of the analysis is presented in Section IV, and Section V summarises the study.

2. Literature Review

Many studies conducted to identify the factors influencing the adoption of cashless payment systems. Users' readiness to go cashless is directly affected by ease of use, usefulness, innovativeness, optimism, and lack of awareness (Balakrishnan et al., 2021). Performance expectancy, facilitating condition, and perceived technology security was found to be the most significant influencing factors towards the adoption of cashless payments (Rahman et al., 2021). Most of the studies found the significance of security in the adoption of digital payment methods. If the risk is low then, people will trust the system which results in the increased adoption of cashless payment systems.

Researchers also used panel data set to identify the influence of different digital payment modes on various economic parameters. In the short period adoption of a cashless payment method will influence other cashless payment system, and cashless payment systems have an impact on the economic growth in the long run (Tee & Ong, 2016). The fixed effect analysis shows that increased volume of digital payments helps an economy to reduce corruption (Kwaku et al., 2021). Immordino & Russo(2017) also found similar result that, credit and debit card payments helps to reduce the VAT evasion.

The micro data analysis on the determinants of card payments reveals that availability, open mindedness and trust have a positive influence, but the macro

data analysis does not support the relevance of education, income, and age (Goczek & Witkowski, 2015). The mobile and internet usage and the level of financial inclusion influence the digital payments in passenger transport (Urbanek, 2021). The study of the relationship between cashless economy policy and financial inclusion discovered that awareness, user value proposition, and infrastructure all have a strong significant influence (Bayero, 2015).

3. Data and Methodology

The study used panel data set of various macroeconomic indicators from nine emerging economies. IMF Identified twenty countries as emerging markets during the period 2010-20, based on the sustained economic growth. These twenty countries actively participating in global trade and financial market integration and accounts for 34 percent of world's nominal GDP (Duttagupta & Pazarbasioglu, 2021). Among the twenty emerging market economies, nine economies having higher digital payment growth potential were selected for the study. They are; Argentina, Brazil, China, India, Indonesia, Russia, Saudi Arabia, South Africa and Turkey. India, china and Russia contributing to the major portion of global electronic payment transactions (Bruno et al., 2020). The CAGR of cashless payment volume for the selected economies during the period 2012-20 are shown in Figure-1. From the data it is clear that the growth of cashless payment for five emerging markets such as, China, India, Indonesia, Russia and Saudi Arabia is impressive.

Figure-1 : CAGR of Cashless Payments Volume (2012-20)

Source : Red Book Statistics-Bank of International Settlement.

The macro economic variables were analysed to identify the drivers of cashless payments. Volume of cashless payment per inhabitant was selected as the proxy for establishing relationship. Six macro economic variables have been selected for testing the relationship towards cashless payments. Data were collected from the Red book statistics of Bank of International Settlement and the World Bank database. The sample period for the study is 2012-2020, and 81 samples were collected. The detailed list of the macro economic variables adopted for the study is given in Table-1.

Table-1 : Summary of Variables Studied

Variables	Description	Source
Cashless payments per inhabitant (CLPV)	Annual cashless payment volume per inhabitant	BIS Statistics
GDP per Capita (GDPPC)	Annual GDP at Current US\$	World bank data bank
Cards per hundred people (CARD)	Total number of payments cards issued per hundred people	BIS Statistics
POS per hundred people (POS)	Total number of pos terminals established per hundred people	BIS Statistics
Inflation (INFL)	Inflation, GDP deflator (annual %)	World bank data bank
Industry Value Added (IVA)	Industry (including construction), value added (% of GDP)	World bank data bank
Internet Usage (INTUSE)	Individuals using the internet (% of population)	World bank data bank

Source : Prepared by the researcher.

4. Data Analysis and Result

Panel data regression method was adopted to identify the relationship between digital payment volume and macro economic variables. Appropriate regression technique will be selected from among Pooled ordinary least square model, Fixed Effect Model (FEM), and Random Effect Model to establish the relationship between variables in the panel data. Breusch-Pagan test and Hausman test were applied to identify the suitable model. The analysis was carried out by importing panel data in E-Views version 12.

4.1. Model Specification

The determinants of cashless payments are analysed using six macro economic variables. They are; GDP per capita, Card per hundred people, POS per hundred people, inflation, Industry value added, and internet usage. The fixed effect model regression equation for panel data is as follows:

$$Y_{it} = a_i + bX_{it} + e_{it}$$

Where Y_{it} is the value of dependent variable (cashless payment volume per inhabitant) of country i at time t . X_{it} is the value of independent variables of country i at time t .

4.2. Descriptive Statistics

The summary of descriptive statistics of seven macro economic variables is given in table 2. Among the countries China and India are the two major fast developing countries and also the largest populated countries globally. They adopted latest mobile and communication technologies to strengthen the cashless payment ecosystems. As a result a rapid growth can be observed in the cashless payment transactions.

Table-2 : Descriptive Statistics

	CLPV	GDPPC	CARD	POS	INFL	IVA	INTUSE
Mean	144.301	9768.61	232.548	1.41787	7.8856	31.4489	56.2423
Maximum	1599.48	25243.6	634.648	6.32106	50.9215	62.6912	97.8600
Minimum	8.59317	1443.88	56.4732	0.06747	-16.909	17.6501	11.1000
S.D	268.998	5869.43	139.478	1.21348	11.0094	10.0678	21.7147

Source : Consolidated by the researcher.

The selected countries have an average of 144.301 cashless payment transactions per inhabitant per year. A higher average GDP per capita value indicates the economies' overall production strength. In these countries, more than 50% of the population uses the internet. However, there is a substantial difference between the maximum and minimum values of the study's parameters. Because emerging markets are fast-growing economies, rapid growth in both economic and non-economic activities has been observed over the last nine years.

4.3. Empirical Result

Pooled ordinary least square model (POLS) has been analysed using Panel least square method, to establish the relationship between Cashless payment Volume per inhabitant and selected macro economic variables. The result of the pooled regression model is presented in Table-3. The result shows that, card per inhabitant, inflation and internet usage were significant at 5% significant level.

Table-3 : Result of Pooled Regression Model (Panel Least Square)

Variable	Co-efficient	S.E	t-Statistics
Constant (C)	-257.7780*	120.9379	-2.131491
GDPPC	0.006316	0.006765	0.933633
CARD	-0.063436**	0.023767	-2.669040
POS	2.907975	3.007501	0.966907
INFL	-6.778680**	2.365754	-2.865336
IVA	5.715984	3.236173	1.766279
INTUSE	5.696003**	1.758682	3.238790
R-squared	0.492583	F-statistic	11.97276
Adjusted R-squared	0.451441	Prob. (F-statistic)	0.000000
SE of Regression	192.2331		

** p <.01, * p <.05

Source : Consolidated by the researcher.

Then we applied Breusch-Pagan (BP) test to identify the suitability of Pooled OLS model. The test result shows that there is cross section random effect in the panel data (Cross section- $p < .05$, Time- $p > .05$). Therefore, in the second stage, one sided random effect model using panel EGLS model has been analysed for the data.

The test result shows that (Table-4), the co-efficient of the model is significant at 5% level. Number of cards, inflation and internet usage were significantly influencing the cashless payment volumes. The suitability of random effect model was tested by conducting Hausman test. The purpose of the test is to

identify whether unique error are correlated with each explanatory variable. The test result reject the null hypothesis ($\chi = 83.939705$; $df = 6$; $p < .05$). Random effect model is not appropriate for the data; hence fixed effect model is used for analysis.

Table-4 : Result of Random Effect Model

Variable	Co-efficient	S.E	t-Statistics
Constant (C)	-255.8764**	95.12346	-2.689940
GDPPC	0.001987	0.004601	0.431764
CARD	-0.065860***	0.018285	-3.601822
POS	2.223789	2.176121	1.021905
INFL	-7.466939***	1.827881	-4.085025
IVA	3.150927	2.501316	1.259707
INTUSE	8.217734***	1.161968	7.072255
R-squared	0.410997	F-statistic	8.606014
Adjusted R-squared	0.363240	Prob. (F-statistic)	0.000000
SE of Regression	166.6994		

*** p <.001, ** p <.01

Source : Consolidated by the researcher.

The result of fixed effect model is shown in table 5. A cross section fixed effect can be observed across the selected countries. The Chow test reject the null hypothesis ($p < 0.05$), which confirm the suitability of fixed effect model over common effect model. Among the six variables, three variables namely, number of cards, industrial value added, and internet usage have significant influence on cashless payments. The constant of the model is also significant at 5% level. Internet usage has a strong positive influence on cashless payment volume, whereas number of cards and industry value added has inverse influence. GDP per capita, number of POS terminals and inflation does not significantly contribute to cashless payment volume. The variables in the model together contribute 85 percent towards cashless payment volume.

Table-5 : Result of Fixed Effect Model

Variable	Co-efficient	S.E	t-Statistics
Constant (C)	552.9921*	261.2866	2.116420
GDPPC	0.018293	0.009601	1.905204
CARD	-0.072644*	0.031910	-2.276550
POS	4.543657	2.921340	1.555333
INFL	2.645832	3.176960	0.832819
IVA	-28.27714***	5.956420	-4.747338
INTUSE	6.855097**	2.036893	3.365467
R-squared	0.849652	F-statistic	26.64153
Adjusted R-squared	0.817760	Prob. (F-statistic)	0.000000
SE of Regression	114.8343		

*** p <.001, ** p <.01, * p <.05

Source : Consolidated by the researcher.

5. Summary and Conclusion

This paper seeks to identify the macroeconomic drivers of cashless payments. Panel data regression model has been analysed by collecting data from 9 emerging market economies. The test result shows that individuals using internet have strong positive influence on cashless payment volume. Most of the cashless payment methods are provided through digital payment modes. So growth in internet connectivity has positive impact on the cashless payment transactions. At the same time number of cards issued by the authority has negative impact on cashless payment transactions. The fast growing technology adoption in emerging markets lead to the development of mobile phone based payment technology. Countries like India, China and Indonesia, focused on mobile based payment system. It may reduce the demand for card payments. Inflation make the economy unstable and higher price of commodities will reduce the transaction volumes of payment transactions. Therefore, a negative influence of inflation can be observed on cashless payment volumes.

The study focused on emerging market to identify the possible influencing factors which facilitate the growth of cashless payments. The analysis revealed a strong positive influence of internet usage on cashless payment and at the same time a

negative influence of inflation, and number of payment cards also observed. The study has certain limitations in the following aspects. Firstly, it focused on the emerging markets and selected 9 economies to collect data. Future research can be conducted similar studies on other economies. Second, six factors have been analysed to identify the influence on cashless payment volume. More number of factors can be incorporated in the future studies. Studies on the factors affecting cashless payment value can also be conducted by the researchers.

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